

MORPHOLOGY-WORD GROUPS AND THEIR CLASSIFICATION.

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Word categories are groups of words in the language that are distinguished based on the presence of a common categorical meaning in them (subjectivity in nouns, action-state in verbs), a single system of grammatical categories, specific word changes, forms and types of word formation, common syntactic tasks (in some literature, "lexicogrammatical categories of words" also called). So, when dividing words into groups, categories, the similarity of their syntactic, morphological and spiritual (semantic) features is taken into account. Phrases are primarily divided into 2 main groups: independent Phrases and non-independent Phrases

- Independent words in Uzbek for the first group,
- and the second group includes auxiliary words, exclamations, taslid words and modal words. Independent words are words that have a lexical meaning and perform a nominative function, that is, they name or refer to an object, event, symbol, action, etc., and can act as an independent part of a sentence.

Words can also be classified according to the position they occupy in a sentence. Words that can stand in the same syntactic position in a sentence or perform the same syntactic function are included in the same word groups. In this case, not only the sum of syntactic tasks is important, but also the degree of specificity of each of these tasks to certain word groups. These tasks are divided into primary and secondary types. For example, in the Uzbek language, as in several other languages, nouns and verbs can take the place of possessives and participles, but for verbs, the participle function is primary, and the possessive function is secondary. Similarly, for nouns, the possessive function is primary, and the possessive function is secondary.

Each word group is distinguished by its own set of grammatical categories. These categories (for example, agreement, possession, number in nouns; degree in adjectives; person-number, inclination, proportion, etc. in verbs) apply to most words in each word group, which is considered a morphological criterion for dividing words into groups.

The system of word groups in modern school grammars, that is, the division of words into groups, goes back to ancient times. In the 4th century BC, Aristotle divided the word groups into 7. av. In the 5th century, Indian linguists divided Yaska and Panini into 4. Later. In the 2nd and 1st centuries, the Alexandrian

philologists Dionysius of Thrace, Apollonius Discolus, and Varro from Rome were divided into 8 groups (autism, verb, adverb, adjective, article, pronoun, auxiliary, conjunction) on mixed morphological, semantic and syntactic bases. In this case, the nouns, in turn, cover noun, adjective and number groups. To some extent, this system of word groups also influenced the Arabic grammatical tradition: Arabs also refer to independent words other than verbs with the term "name". In the following periods (the Middle Ages and the 19th and 20th centuries), several classifications were made in this regard in European and Russian linguistics, but they were often based on the Alexandrian classification. In different languages, the number of word groups and the size of some groups are different. For example, the number of word groups in modern Russian is often indicated as 10, and in Uzbek as 10-12 (different textbooks). These are 6 independent (noun, adjective, number, pronoun, adverb and verb), 3 auxiliary (helper, conjunction, predicate) and 3 individual (pronouns, similes, modal words) word groups. The non-stabilization of the number of word groups indicates the need to conduct new research in this field in the future.